

Adaptive SAR Signal Compression Through Artificial Intelligence

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The volume of data captured by modern SAR instruments and constellations is immense, and satellite downlink capacities will not keep pace with the data explosion caused by the growth in the commercial SAR sector. This has resulted in a bottleneck, hindering high-value data from reaching end-users efficiently. In response, this work took a novel approach to focus on enhancing raw data compression using machine learning (ML) models. These models are designed to select the most effective compression algorithms based on the content inferred from the raw data. Processing SAR data on-board satellites is traditionally challenging due to the high computational complexity. The ability to infer information from data without creating SAR images, as demonstrated in this work, is a significant breakthrough. We present the results from the ML based compression selector over different scenes with a range of configurable parameters weighting different factors combined with a decision tree error prediction for the final data compression. Finally, future hardware feasibility and capability is assessed, targeting a Smallsat SAR mission, with a high level roadmap developed to progress the concept toward this goal.

1 Introduction

The value of SAR in comparison to electro-optical imaging technologies is the ability to image in all-weather and all-lighting conditions which allows customers to build dense time series over areas of interest. The deployment of constellations of spaceborne SAR platforms enhances this capability. SAR also offers some unique applications based on the physics of the received signal. Due to the ability to measure both magnitude and phase of signals at microwave frequencies of the EM spectrum, processing techniques can be applied to make measurements that are not possible with the radiometric measurements of electro-optical devices. Space-based SAR interferometry is an application that has seen widespread use in fields like seis-

mology, disaster management and topographic measurement [1–3]. The active nature of the SAR instrument also allows control of the polarization of emitted signals, allowing the recording of the polarization behaviour of scatterers on the ground. From these measurements we can extract information such as land-use classification, agricultural monitoring and forest biomass estimation [4–7].

Spaceborne SAR system architectures are undergoing a step change in that it is becoming possible to deploy large constellations of satellites as opposed to a single instrument or pair of satellites [8, 9]. The multitude of commercial companies in the SAR observation market not only augment current services but provide new capabilities such as Distributed Radar Image Formation Technology (DRIFT) [10]. On larger SAR missions, the trend is toward electronically steerable active phased array antenna and multi-beam/multi-frequency instruments [11, 12]. The sheer amount of data generated by these instruments presents a system-level challenge for space-ground downlink that requires novel approaches to overcome. It likely will not be possible to simply increase downlink capacity due to satellite power and bandwidth constraints and the limited spectrum available due to radio license constraints. It is from these system-level motivations that the desire for more effective on-board compression stem.

2 Methodology

Described in the following sections is the rationale for the selection of specific compression methods that were chosen between by the ML component, along with how the dataset was built for the ML demonstrator that was used to generate the results.

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Figure 1: Compression algorithm evaluation methodology

2.1 Raw SAR Data Compression

A survey of SAR data compression algorithms was used to make a sub-selection of algorithms to utilise during the AI/ML Demonstrator Development stage of the work. The standard algorithm in the field of raw SAR data compression is Block Adaptive Quantization (BAQ) [13]. The benefits of using BAQ as a base algorithm are that it is simple to implement in hardware, well tested and documented. There are evolutions on the BAQ technique such as Entropy Constrained Block Adaptive Quantization, Block Adaptive Vector Quantization, Flexible Block Adaptive Quantization, and others [14–17]. They all improve the basic BAQ technique but at the price of added complexity, which is a significant concern when considering future hardware implementations. Following the survey, the following algorithms were then implemented and analysed:

- BAQ
- FBAQ
- FFT-BAQ

A set of statistical metrics was used to assess the performance of compression methods on raw SAR data. These include dynamic range (ratio of brightest vs darkest pixel), and for magnitude and phase of the raw data: mean, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis and entropy. The methodology for evaluating the performance of the selected compression algorithms against raw SAR data, using both image domain and statistical metrics, is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 2: ML dataset generation methodology

2.2 ML Model Development and Demonstrator

To train the ML model, a dataset was developed which would allow the prediction of the compression performance in the image domain from statistical measurements in the raw data domain. The raw data input features that were to be ingested by the model included the mean, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis, as mentioned in the previous section. Additionally, statistical tests such as the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. These features were selected as they combine to give a measure of the Gaussian nature of the data. It is known that the BAQ algorithm performs optimally on data that is normally distributed so these features provide a measure of the compression algorithm performance. Due to this, it was therefore hypothesised that it should be possible to train a model to predict the compression performance in the image domain from the resulting focused images - chosen to be measured by signal-to-quantisation-noise-ratio (SQNR) - from these simple statistics in the raw data domain. The dataset used to train the final model was generated as per Figure 2.

Several models were assessed for implementation such as: K-nearest neighbours (KNN), decision trees, support vector regression, and linear regression. The trade-offs of each of these models were compared such as their ability to handle multiple outputs, their complexity and their initial training accuracy. From these trade-offs, the two highest performing models (KNN and decision tree) were selected for further development with decision tree being the model that was finally chosen with results shown below. The decision tree model was trained on the dataset described above

Figure 3: Predictions against the true metric values for all compression methods

Figure 4: Predictions from decision tree algorithm over a scene for lowest bit rate BAQ

with a grid search carried out to avoid model over-fitting. The parameter grid was focused on tree depth and how the tree is split with the final parameters selected being:

- Maximum tree depth = 15
- Maximum number of samples required to be left at a leaf node = 2
- Minimum samples required to split an internal node = 5

Figure 3 displays the predicted values against the true values that were previously calculated as part of the test dataset with the dotted line showing perfect predictions. This gave a prediction accuracy of 0.974 in the R^2 score and 1.09 in the mean squared error over the test dataset.

Figure 4 shows a scatter plot of the true SDNR values with the decision tree predictions. These were

taken over a full scene showing the SDNR for the co-polarisation. The spikes seen in the data are mis-predictions from the machine learning model where the model may still be over-fitting to the training data. Although these may cause single range windows to be compressed with a non-optimal compression algorithm, the model accuracy over the whole scene will ensure that the correct compression algorithm will be chosen most of the time thus incurring the benefit of using the ML based approach. These predictions could be improved by increasing the amount of training data with a wide range of clutter in the scenes allowing the entire range of input space to be seen by the model. It is also yet to be investigated if the size of the range line window would affect the accuracy of the model, as there could be range lines in these windows which are dominating the average used for the feature vector and thus causing mis-detections.

To be able to select the correct compression algorithm and achieve the desired bitrate, post-processing logic was implemented to combine the output of the ML model and user defined parameters such as the error threshold, the desired bit rate and computation complexity weightings. This was done with the aim of achieve a quantization error that is equal to or less than a user defined threshold while minimising the bitrate or computational complexity of the compression. Bitrate and computational complexity weightings are used to set an order of preference of algorithms to be selected, depending on the given use case.

3 Results

The ML enabled decision module was deployed against various test scenes, with different user defined parameters. The results for two scenarios are included below, demonstrating the module’s selection of the

most appropriate compression algorithm in each case.

3.1 Scenario 1: Error Threshold

In the scenario shown in Figure 5, a test was carried out to show that the predictor and decision function could switch compression algorithm while maintaining an overall SDNR figure above the set threshold. It would also give an indication of where and how switching would occur, with the initial hypothesis that the algorithm would switch to lower bitrates in areas with less cultural clutter. The decision function parameters used for this test were:

Parameter	Value
Error Threshold [dB]	15
Complexity Weight	0
Bit-rate Weight	0

Table 1: User defined parameters for scenario 1

Over regions in the Aurora test scene where there is greater cultural clutter (and more heterogeneity) present in the data, the BAQ4 algorithm has been selected. Over more homogeneous regions (where fields can be seen in the data), the BAQ3 algorithm has been selected. In conclusion, the decision module has selected a more complex algorithm (BAQ4) for the job of compressing a heterogeneous scene, and a less accurate algorithm (BAQ3) for compressing a homogeneous scene to achieve the same SDNR in both cases.

3.2 Scenario 2: Weighted Bit-rate

This scenario tested the decision module in meeting multiple constraints: a minimum error threshold had to be maintained (as in Scenario 1) while also maintaining a maximum average bit-rate. This was designed to exercise the use of more computationally complex algorithms which could meet these dual constraints of minimising both error and bit-rate whilst trading off on increased computation. The decision function parameters were set to:

Parameter	Value
Error Threshold [dB]	15
Complexity Weight	0
Bit-rate Weight	4.5

Table 2: User defined parameters for scenario 2

It is shown in Figure 6 that the higher bit rate algorithms are selected for the job of compressing regions with most cultural clutter. In conclusion, the decision module has penalised higher bit rate algorithms

Figure 5: Compression algorithm selection across Aurora test scene

when meeting this user set constraint. This scenario also highlights the use of the FFTBAQ algorithms to achieve a higher accuracy whilst maintaining a lower bitrate, although this comes at the cost of higher computational complexity. Where FFTBAQ was used here, it was predicted to still meet the set error threshold of 15dB whereas BAQ2 was not.

4 Discussion

With SAR instruments acquiring data at rates of Gbps when observing, on-board data handling and down-linking through the space-ground link is a challenge. Any effort to reduce this on-board will provide increases in system capacity. The motivations for better on-board compression of raw SAR data are therefore:

- The low duty cycle of SAR instruments
- Lowering on-board storage requirements or in-

Figure 6: Compression algorithm selection across Aurora test scene when decision module prioritises lower bit rate

creasing number of acquisitions that can be stored on-board

- Reducing the size of data that needs to be down-linked

Considering the feasibility of deploying the ML-enabled decision module onboard, the ML model that has been generated uses a small number of statistical metrics as input features. Many of these would be calculated anyway for the standard onboard compression algorithms, so it follows that these features or similar could be generated from the raw data, on-the-fly, at the rate of data acquisition. Onboard inference could be implemented on FPGA using tools like Vitis AI. It has been demonstrated that inference of SDNR in the image domain is possible from features derived from statistics in the raw data domain. A neural network (as a universal function approximator) could be trained to map these features to SDNR. Neural networks have a well-trodden path to implementation

on hardware and there are software/hardware development toolchains available for further optimization of the onboard implementation e.g. weight quantization, connection pruning.

A Hardware Roadmap was created which compares two approaches to the hardware architecture: runtime compression versus offline compression. NovaSAR-S was considered as a potential future target hardware system. It provides a good candidate for comparing a runtime compression mode with an offline compression operating mode, as it currently operates runtime compression and SSTL (Surrey Satellite Technology Ltd) are actively exploring offline on-board payload data processing architectures. One such project is the Incubated funded Flexible Intelligent Payload Chain (FIPC) where SSTL partnered with Craft Prospect Ltd and University of Surrey as application developers for an offline on-board processor designed to integrate the platform to process data from optical EO payloads. Offline compression modes were found to be the preferred option, at least initially as they required the least modification of radar backend architectures like Airbus DS NIA Radar Backend (as used on NovaSAR).

5 Conclusions

This work demonstrated that the execution of machine learning models working on raw SAR data to perform predictions of reconstruction error in the image domain with various raw SAR data compression algorithms is feasible, albeit with a limited number of end-to-end solutions available when compatibility of all the elements is considered. Many iterations of refinement are expected before an optimal solution can be found. The achievements in the work have applications across several institutional and commercial programmes. On-board processing to improve data compression has many benefits to the EOEP (Earth Observation Envelope Programme) in terms of eliminating or reducing data bottlenecks in EO missions, improving on-board data management, and reducing operational and infrastructure costs. This also benefits Science and Robotic Exploration missions (such as future interplanetary exploration missions with radar payloads), as better data compression can increase the possible scientific return of the mission. A secondary outcome of this work was the development of a machine learning ready raw SAR dataset and a pipeline for generating further datasets, which could be adapted to other applications to enable rapid prototyping of new machine learning methods in the raw SAR domain. Much further development is expected in this area. In future work, the demonstrated algorithms could be embedded in a more realistic mission

concept and demonstrated in simulation, with requirements preferably solicited from stakeholders with real use cases. The suggestions of the Hardware Roadmap should be further assessed, and followed to demonstrate the scheme on representative flight hardware.

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